

ECOFEMINISM AND THE ENVIRONMENTAL LITERATURE OF PAKISTAN: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

This article explores how ecofeminist concepts intersect with literary representations and how they influence Pakistani environmental consciousness. The study uses a systematic review methodology and pulls from current literature on gender, environment, and feminism. A selection of pertinent publications for the study is produced by data screening from Google Scholar, Science Direct, and Academia. This article investigates the efforts of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), particularly the Aurat Foundation and LEAD, to advance environmental awareness, education, and women's empowerment. The study also highlights the significance of women's participation in sustainable development by synthesizing studies on indigenous perspectives on gender and environment. The theoretical foundations examine the connection between gender, nature, and environmental issues. Discussed are the obstacles and prospects facing ecofeminism in Pakistan, with a particular emphasis on governance that is sensitive to gender. The report offers policy implications and proposals in its conclusion, including a legislative framework for ecofeminist and gender-responsive governance. The study offers a thorough grasp of how ecofeminist ideas might help address environmental issues within Pakistan's particular setting.

Keywords: Ecofeminism, Pakistani Environmental Consciousness, Gender-Responsive Policies, Women's Empowerment.

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of Environmental Challenges in Pakistan

Pakistan is situated in the easternmost basin of the Tigris-Euphrates, the Egyptian, and the Indus, the three great rivers that crisscross the steppe desert of the ancient world and were the cradles of early civilizations. Because of this, the Indus River Basin in South Asia is unique compared to other river basins in the area. The country, which gained its independence in 1947, is home to over 0.8 million square kilometers. The region spans latitudes 4°N to 37°N and

longitudes 61°E to 77° 45 E. It is split into two federally controlled regions, the Federally controlled Tribal Area and the Federally Administered Capital Territory, and five provinces, namely Balochistan, Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Gilgit Baltistan, for management and administration purposes. The divisions, districts, tehsils, cities, and mauzas (revenue villages) that make up each province are further divided (Park, 2013).

Numerous environmental challenges have been brought to light by recent studies carried out in

Pakistan by the government. In general, irrigated agriculture, water, energy, waste management, pollution, and biodiversity are the areas of concern. All things considered; these studies show a decline in each of these categories. The health of individuals is still greatly impacted by the rising levels of pollution in the air, water, and land, particularly that of vulnerable populations like children. Water, trees, and other vegetation, as well as important biological habitats, are examples of renewable natural resources whose quantity and quality have decreased. While there have been occasional outliers, like the transport subsector's move to cleaner fuels, the public, business, and civil society have not sufficiently responded to these issues. The ensuing subsections expand upon the analytical work conducted on Pakistan's primary environmental difficulties and challenges, outlining current developments in these areas (Essakali, 2005; World Bank, 2006; United Nations Development Programme, 2013).

Top environmental challenges in the nation revolve around managing limited natural resources (green issues), addressing waste and pollution (brown issues), and preparing for potential vulnerabilities to natural disasters and climate change (Asian Development Bank, 2008). Due to ecologically damaging practices and the country's rapidly growing population, Pakistan's natural resources are facing increasing strain. As a result, the nation is now considered one of the most water-stressed countries, with its renewable freshwater sources being depleted at an alarming rate. The diversion of water for agriculture has significantly reduced the flow of freshwater in Pakistan's rivers. Furthermore, the inefficiency of canal irrigation has led to the salinization of soil, negatively impacting crop production. The excessive and improper use of pesticides has also disrupted the natural balance of agricultural soils, resulting in a decline in the diversity of invertebrate fauna. The country's natural forest cover is also reportedly decreasing, which has significant implications for irrigation, biodiversity, and crucial ecological services. The usual breeding sites for sea life that is significant to the economy, mangroves, have also decreased. Similar to this, a large rise in livestock grazing has resulted in considerable degradation of Pakistan's arid and semi-arid rangelands. Future trends and possibilities are highly dependent on social

responses and climate conditions. In Pakistan, pollution brought on by ineffective management has become a serious environmental issue. Pakistan has become more dependent on imported fossil fuels because of its expanding energy consumption needs over time. Its limited institutional and technological capacity has prevented it from making significant progress toward energy efficiency. For impoverished urban and rural households who rely on biomass for cooking, especially during the winter, indoor air pollution is a major contributor to the widespread cases of chronic bronchitis and other respiratory diseases. Some of the best soils and water resources in the nation are being contaminated by industrial discharges (of hazardous and persistent pollutants). When solid trash is burned or placed on low-lying land, it can contaminate groundwater, produce dust, or release carcinogens that are harmful to human health. Fresh water sources for customers downstream are being contaminated by the dumping of untreated urban sewage. A major contributing reason to the high prevalence of diseases like diarrhoea in the nation is inadequate access to safe drinking water supplies as well as poor sanitation and hygiene (Imran et al., 2021). Pakistan is confronted with environmental difficulties arising from natural disasters such as floods, earthquakes, droughts, and cyclones. The country is prone to flooding, with frequent earthquakes and droughts occurring in vulnerable areas. In addition, cyclones have a significant impact on coastal regions and can devastate crops located hundreds of kilometers away. The escalation of temperatures can result in more frequent droughts and a decrease in crop yield, while an increase in flooding can lead to the destruction of irrigation systems (Syed et al., 2022).

1.2. Emergence of Ecofeminism in the Global Context

A novel approach to feminist philosophy, ecofeminism was developed in the 1970s by French feminist Françoise d'Eaubonne. Because of its goal to dismantle the institutions and structures that confine feminism as a philosophy, it attracted the attention of environmentalists, peace activists, and feminists alike. Ecofeminism examines issues that have an impact on modern society, such as environmental preservation and

gender equality, and views oppression as a systemic process that aims to remove dominance. According to the idea, society has been built with the supremacy of patriarchal principles as a top priority. It also recognizes that oppressed groups can work together to demolish the existing social hierarchy. The idea draws parallels between the oppression of the environment and the dominance of women by utilizing intersectionality, which is the interconnectivity of identification features. Power and dominance battles are taking place among all marginalized groups. This is not intended to minimize the unique experiences of any person or group. Instead, it teaches activists about oppressive strategies and the necessity of collaborative efforts among activist movements. Ecofeminism aims to promote both inclusion and unity among marginalized groups by advocating for grassroots efforts such as organizing rallies and encouraging bottom-up decision-making. These activities serve to evaluate and challenge the dominant groups' control and impact, as stated in a report by 1 Million Women in 2017.

Objectives and Scope of the Systematic Review

1.3. Research Questions

1. How is environmental management in Pakistan impacted by indigenous knowledge that adheres to ecofeminist principles?

2. What role do ecofeminist themes have in promoting environmental consciousness in Pakistani literature? How are they portrayed in these works?

1.4. Objectives

1. Examine how Indigenous knowledge, in line with ecofeminist ideals, is used to Pakistani environmental management.
2. Examine how ecofeminist issues are portrayed in Pakistani literature and how they have influenced the development of environmental consciousness.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study's approach was derived from a review of recent feminism and environment research articles that addressed gender or environment topics.

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) method, proposed by Moher et al. (2009), was utilized as the basis for the systematic review. This approach provides guidelines and directives for conducting a rigorous systematic review in accordance with scientific criteria. We have delineated a series of stages, which are expounded upon in the works of (Petticrew and Roberts, 2006; Sovacool et al., 2018).

Figure 1: That is described below (Petticrew and Roberts, 2006; Sovacool et al., 2018).

3.1. Data Extraction and Analysis

We employed a database comprising multiple descriptive information categories to capture the metadata for every chosen study and retrieve information from our literature review (Table 1). Thanks to our study objectives and analytical frame of reference, we were able to establish multiple variables, categories, and codes

beforehand, or a priori, for our analysis. The descriptive variables considered in our literature review (Sanz-Hernández et al., 2022) included the publication year and journal, geographical scope, affiliation and gender of the first author, economic sector, gender centrality, article contribution (based on Sovacool et al., 2018), and dominant research methods.

Table 2: Descriptive variables analyzed

Variable code	Typology	Description and utility	Codes	
Journal	Continuous text variable	Journal which publishes the article.	Open	
Title	Continuous text variable	Full headline.	Open	
Authors	Continuous text variable	Authors' names articles.	Open	
Publication year	Discrete variable	Publication date.	From 2000 to 2020	
Author's gender	Discrete variable	Based on the names, presentations of the authors in the articles and photographs on websites, we have determined their gender in order to find out if these variable conditions the interest in developing the relationship between ecofeminism and gender. Despite the current difficulties to know the gender identity of the authors formally, we wanted to try to get closer to this information.	Female Male	
Location	Discrete variable	Geographical setting to which the study refers. To find out in which regions most research is being done on the relationship between ecofeminism and gender.	Africa Asia Europe Latin America North America	Oceania Various (or comparative studies between regions)
Country- Corresponding author	Continuous text variable	Country to which the author's university belongs. It is relevant to know from which regions they are most concerned with understanding or linking gender and ecofeminism.	Open	
Where	Discrete variable	The first placement of the word "gender" or "women" in the article. Locating where these words appear is an objective way of measuring their prominence in the article.	Title Abstract Keywords	Main text Conclusions References
Centrality	Discrete variable	Centrality of the gender issue in the article. We assess the relevance of the gender issue throughout the article. We consider high centrality when gender is actually the central theme of the article. Low centrality when only the words gender or women are mentioned somewhere in the article.	High Medium Low	
Article contribution	Discrete variable	The type of contribution of the article. Depending on the focus of the article, it will produce more or less practical contributions that help to the development of the ecofeminism and the gender issue. The main general contributions can be: empirical (new applications or existing methods or theories, or new types of evidence), theoretical (reporting a new theory or testing an existing theory), and finally, methodological (developing or contributing to new methods) (Sovacool et al., 2018).	Theoretical Methodological Empirical	
Dominant research method	Discrete variable	Methodology used in the study. Knowing the technique used in the study helps us to better understand its purpose and how practical its contribution to the research paradigm is.	Case studies Data analysis (secondary sources and statistics) Experiments Survey	Qualitative research (interviews, speech analysis...) Review Other

3.2. Data Screening and Data Base

Serial No	Data Base	Data Screening
1.	Google Scholar	15,400
2.	Science Direct	4,217
3.	Academia	8,675

4. GENDERED PERSPECTIVES ON ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN PAKISTAN

The potential danger posed to both humanity and life on Earth by significant shifts in environmental patterns highlights the importance of considering gender perspectives. This is necessary due to the unequal social roles and rights between males and females. In order to achieve sustainable development and preserve the environment, it is crucial to prioritize environmental education and the empowerment of women, as stated by (Sengwar, 2015). Therefore, to ensure that their citizens are concerned about both the role of gender in environmental sensitivity emerging nations like Pakistan must encourage environmental education and women's engagement. Environmental education accomplishes this by fostering behaviors, knowledge, skills, motivation, and commitment in individuals and groups to address gender and environmental challenges (Sola, 2014).

According to earlier studies, environmental education programs and sustainable development strategies that did not support and foster equal participation from both sexes, especially the empowerment of women, have typically fallen short of their goals. In *Woman's Role in Economic Development*, Boserup made the case that gender inequality behaviors perpetuate women's oppression and marginalization within a variety of patriarchal and socioeconomic systems (Boserup, 1970). One of the primary objectives of the 1978 intergovernmental conferences on environmental education, organized by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNESCO-UNEP), was to promote the inclusion of women in environmental awareness initiatives. The UN conferences recognized the significance of educating about sustainable development and ensuring equal participation of women (UNESCO-UNEP, 1978). Furthermore, women's engagement was acknowledged as being crucial to

the sustainable development goal in the framework of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Any initiative is unlikely to succeed without the full participation of women, given their role as advocates for their communities in carrying out household tasks, achieving food and nutrition security, enhancing the standard of living for families, especially in rural areas, caring for the elderly and children, and promoting general societal well-being (UNESCO, 2005).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) replaced the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in September 2015 and thus reinforced the objective of equal education for all genders. SDG 4 emphasizes community environmental education in addition to "ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all". Despite this, several studies show that, in contrast to men, women are still unable to fully engage in environmental education programs because of powerful patriarchal structures that prioritize the voices of men over those of women (Chifamba, 2013; FAO, 2011). Women are still largely marginalized in society and excluded from environmental education programs (Alam, 2017; Chifamba, 2013; Roy, 2014). Additionally, prior research indicates that women's involvement in various forms of research is gauged by the number of participants in Consortium for Energy Efficiency (CEE) programs and activities in establishments and organizations that give women's lived experiences less consideration (Imran & Hart, 2019; Mai et al., 2011; Sultana, 2014).

Prior research has examined gender disparities in a variety of fields, including behavior, attitude, and involvement in environmental issues (Agarwal, 1992; Alston, 2014). Research has confirmed that the degree of gender engagement varies depending on one's education level and level of topic awareness when it comes to participation in public discussions. While environmental education and awareness have not been extensively used, general education is helping to improve women's status in developing nations including Bangladesh, Pakistan, India, and Afghanistan (Imran et al., 2020). The study aims to highlight the significance of gender empowerment and the sensitivity of emancipation in such societies where women are

responsible for the private sphere because, as Sakellari and Skanavis (2013) state, “the subject of gender remains marginal to the field of environmental education research” (p. 81). Pakistan has been dealing with several environmental problems, according to a 2005 report by the Environmental Protection Authority of Pakistan. These problems include the country's fast-changing climate, a lack of clean drinking water, biodiversity loss, overpopulation, deforestation, and pollution of all kinds, including air, land, water, and noise (Environmental Protection Agency [EPA] Pakistan, 2005). According to recent studies, Pakistan's population may suffer from climate change's tremendous effects on the country's economy, society, and environment (Khan et al., 2016). As a result, Pakistan has experienced the most severe effects of global warming and climate change. The average yearly temperature increase over the past century has been 0.6 °C (Khan et al., 2016), while the UNDP (2006) reports that

Pakistan has had an average temperature increase of 0.08 °C every decade. Furthermore, Pakistan contributes comparatively less to the release of greenhouse gases than other nations, which means that these gases have a significant impact on the country's climate. The country's economy is losing almost 5% of its gross domestic product (GDP), or nearly \$5 billion, annually as a result of the country's fast-changing environment in the southern and northern regions, where the ratios are 0.6 and 0.8, respectively (UNDP, 2006). Due to catastrophic climate change, almost 10 million people have been impacted and forced to relocate during the past two years. The vulnerability index¹ placed Pakistan 12th out of 193 countries in the world due to economic losses of about US\$4.5 billion; because of extreme climate change, and livestock are predicted to suffer more from ongoing temperature increases. (Ahmed & Schmitz, 2011). According to Table 1, Pakistan was ranked among the top 10 nations from 1998 to 2017 by the Global Climate Change Index 2019.

Table 3: Ten Most Affected Countries Highlighted in the Long-Term CRI 1998–2017.

Country	CRI 1998–2017 (1997–2016)	CRI score	Death toll	Deaths per 100,000 inhabitants	Total losses in million US\$ PPP	Losses per unit GDP in %	Number of events (total 1998–2017)
Puerto Rico	1 (100)	7.83	150.05	4.061	5,033.16	4.204	25
Honduras	2 (1)	13.00	302.45	4.215	556.56	1.846	66
Myanmar	3 (3)	13.17	7,048.85	14.392	1,275.96	0.661	47
Haiti	4 (2)	15.17	281.30	2.921	418.21	2.642	77
Philippines	5 (5)	19.67	867.40	0.971	2,932.15	0.576	307
Nicaragua	6 (4)	20.33	163.60	2.945	223.25	1.009	45
Bangladesh	7 (6)	26.67	635.50	0.433	2,403.84	0.640	190
Pakistan	8 (7)	30.17	512.40	0.315	3,826.03	0.567	145
Vietnam	9 (8)	31.67	296.40	0.350	2,064.74	0.516	220
Dominica	10 (44)	33.00	3.35	4.718	132.59	21.205	8

Note: CRI = Climate Risk Index; GDP = gross domestic product; PPP = purchasing power parity.

The table mentioned earlier illustrates the extent to which Pakistan's climate change has impacted the lives of men and women, especially those who engage in outdoor and agricultural pursuits. Since most of their jobs are related to raising livestock, farming, and the production of clay bricks, more than 60.78% of the population lives in rural areas and is directly impacted by climate change (Pakistan: Rural Population, 2016).

5. Environmental Issues and Women in Pakistan

There is an unbreakable bond and mutual reliance between women and the environment. Everyone must maintain the environment since the industrial revolutions, environmental changes have had a disproportionately long-lasting impact on civilization. In this sense, individuals can contribute significantly (Rahman, 2015). Therefore, considering the elements that significantly affect people's lives is necessary when examining the environment from a social and

cultural perspective. Some of these traits include ecozones; others include socioeconomic position; gender; health; race, ethnicity, religion, and class in connection to their place-based contexts. Segnestam (2015) said, Unfortunately, due to societal, cultural, and religious restrictions, women in Pakistan are not granted the same rights as males in numerous areas. According to recent studies, women's employment in Pakistan has been significantly impacted by environmental challenges and climate change. This is because women make up 74.2% of the workforce in the agriculture sector, compared to men's 34.7%. The ecology and weather patterns in Pakistan are changing worryingly, making women more vulnerable. Previous natural disaster statistics in Pakistan indicate that women were primarily impacted. According to Maplecroft's Climate Change Vulnerability Index (CCVI), approximately 713,000 women aged 15 to 49 and 133,000 pregnant women were affected by the 2010 floods (Shirkat Gah, 2011).

6. Ecofeminist Responses To Environmental Injustices In Pakistan

6.1. Review of Studies Documenting Ecofeminist Activism in Pakistan

This part centres on the in-depth case studies of the two NGOs that were chosen based on their contributions to women's empowerment, environmental education, and awareness in Pakistan.

a) LEAD

The non-profit organization LEAD was founded in January 2005 in Islamabad, Pakistan, with a focus on environmental conservation and developing leaders. It is run by an independent policy think tank with an emphasis on research, public policy engagement (PPE), the development of human leadership, and the corporate and non-profit sectors. In addition, LEAD oversees several separate initiatives, including the Water Program, Social Capital Development, Climate Action, and Leadership Development programs. Three specific initiatives have been created by LEAD to advance development and the environment in Pakistan: The Journey of Pakistan toward 2047, the Knowledge Hub on SDGs, and the Sustainable Cities Project. Its main goals include providing insurance for Pakistan's most disadvantaged

people, as well as entrepreneurship education and skill development for women in Pakistan. Recently, LEAD developed a program to develop the political and leadership skills of women elected in local body elections in KPK, district Chitral, through its suggested intervention, Environment, and Development Leadership Initiatives.

In addition to the programs mentioned above, LEAD also manages a variety of other initiatives. One of these is Fridays for Future, a campaign that is part of the global youth climate strike movement and aims to advocate for action against climate change. Another project under LEAD Pakistan is Entrepreneurship Education and Skills Development for Women through School-Based Productive Enterprises.

b) Aurat Foundation (Woman Foundation)

In order to advance the empowerment of women and democratic governance, the establishment of the Aurat Foundation took place in Islamabad, Pakistan in 1986, as a non-governmental organization operating on a national level. The foundation has branches in all four provinces of Pakistan, namely Lahore, Karachi, Peshawar, and Quetta, in addition to its main headquarters in the capital city. From its inception in 1986, the organization has been dedicated to educating the public on the importance of creating a society in Pakistan that is both democratic and compassionate, where individuals of all genders can live together with honor and regard. The Aurat Foundation has gained widespread recognition, both domestically and internationally, as a leading organization in establishing and strengthening civil society networks and associations. This non-governmental organization's main goals are to enhance women's access to institutions, knowledge, and resources, promote positive attitudes and behaviors that support social environments, and encourage citizens to actively engage in social change and governance processes. (Aurat Foundation (Woman Foundation), 2019).

6.2. Exploration of Women's Roles in Grassroots Environmental Movements

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) utilize various methods to attain their goals, including both top-down and bottom-up approaches. The

bottom-up approach involves working with the community, grassroots projects, and local decision-making groups, known as service delivery groups. On the other hand, the top-down

approach involves engaging in discussions with government agencies and other policy-making bodies.

Table 4: NGOs' Structural Work to Educate and Empower Women in Pakistan.

Serial number	Name of NGO	Strategic women's needs	Practical women's needs
1	LEAD, Pakistan	Capacity building Leadership development Research, assessment Policy making	Rehabilitation Confidence building Establishment of women's institutions Poverty elevation, environmental awareness Climate change and water scarcity campaigns
2	Aurat Foundation	Gender awareness of basic human rights Highlight all kinds of violence against women Legal protection Lobbying for approving women-related ordinances Speak for IDPs rights and direct action for them	Economic development Social empowerment Education for women ² and girls Confidence building Awareness about environmental issues Psychological mobile units in natural disaster areas Temporary shelters for earthquake and floods victims

Note: NGO = nongovernmental organization; LEAD = Leadership for Environment and Development; IDP = internally displaced person.

7. Policy Making and Legislation for Women's Development and Environmental Awareness

NGOs are becoming increasingly involved in the development of laws, policies, and regulations. In line with this trend, LEAD and the Aurat Foundation are dedicated to implementing initiatives that promote the rights and empowerment of women in Pakistan. The Aurat Foundation spearheaded a national campaign in the 1990s to secure a 33% quota for women in the assembly during Pakistani elections. Additionally, the foundation has coordinated multiple citizen campaigns in 1998-1999, 2000, and 2005 to ensure and maximize the representation of women in local government elections. With the support of the Pakistani government, this NGO has successfully passed laws addressing various concerns related to women.

1. Acid Control and Prevention Bill.
2. Modification to the Pakistan Penal Code (Section 59 of XLV of 1860).
3. The 1898 Code of Criminal Procedure (Act V of 1898).
4. Protection Against Harassment of Women at the Workplace 2010 and Protection of Women (Criminal Law Amendment Act, 2006; Anum, n.d.).
5. Women in Distress and Detention Fund Act (XV of 1996).

6. Anti-Women Practices Bill (Criminal Law Amendment 2011).

In a parallel manner, LEAD Pakistan has progressively adapted its aim to incorporate cutting-edge investigation from its initiatives in policy and action research, transforming into a valuable and influential tool for supporting decision makers. This program has been labelled as PPE by LEAD to guarantee consistent triumph and to establish LEAD Pakistan as a valuable resource for shaping national policies. These are some examples of the policy briefings that LEAD co-organized with various organizations, such as the Ministry of Climate Change, including Pakistan's Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC).

1. Prospects and issues for sustainable groundwater management in Pakistan.
2. Taking a gendered approach to climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction.
3. Achieving the SDGs while putting cities first.
4. Motivating Pakistani women to advance and succeed from data to law.
5. Mapping impoverished areas to ensure that nobody is left behind.
6. Impacts of the twenty-first-century climate shift on surface water availability.
7. A fair assessment of the urban infrastructure for clean drinking water in Faisalabad.

8. Challenges And Opportunities For Ecofeminism In Pakistan

8.1. Synthesis of Studies Analysing Critiques and Debates within Ecofeminist Movements

The role of gender is crucial in both environmental concerns and economic progress. Gender inequality in employment, differences in the activities and resources available to men and women, educational achievements, and opportunities for involvement in decision-making all influence gender performance (UNEP, 2015). Therefore, incorporating a gender-sensitive approach in environmental education would improve its effectiveness in reaching marginalized communities, including tribal groups, minorities, and indigenous populations, where gender stereotypes still persist (Sakellari & Skanavis, 2013).

The participants have highlighted the valuable role that women have in implementing eco-friendly initiatives and promoting awareness among their families, communities, and others regarding women's empowerment, environmental concerns, and climate change as their top priority. However, the primary responsibility placed on women for household duties such as cooking, cleaning, doing laundry, taking care of children, and providing basic education can pose more risks for them, as two respondents mentioned in their interviews. Even if they have other jobs, women with extensive knowledge about domestic matters are often solely held responsible for them. This highlights the urgent need for gender equality in education in Pakistan. Otherwise, women's exposure to the environment and their close proximity to it may make them more vulnerable to becoming victims rather than leaders and influential figures in discussions and decision-making processes related to the environment (Imran et al., 2021).

8.2. Evaluation of Barriers to the Integration of Ecofeminist Principles

Ecofeminism aims to achieve two important objectives: the liberation of nature and women. It strives to uncover the underlying link between the domination of gender and the domination of nature. By examining the root causes of the overall dominance system, ecofeminism integrates the theory of the relationship between women and nature into various social structures. It also embraces the diverse perspectives of

women from different ages, races, and social classes. This concept of female and ecological principles, which are the core beliefs of ecofeminism, has been evident across various cultures. (Warren & Cheney, 1991) emphasized the fundamental tenet of ecofeminism by highlighting the principles of femininity and the natural world. In particular, the following four elements comprise the fundamental tenet of ecofeminism:

- a) There are significant connections between the subjugation of nature and women.
- b) A thorough comprehension of these relationships is required to properly comprehend how women and the environment are oppressed.
- c) The ecological perspective needs to be incorporated into feminism's philosophy and practice.
- d) The feminist perspective needs to be included in the solution of ecological issues.

Green feminism is "feminine." Ecofeminism is oriented towards and from women. Ecofeminism highlights the distinctions between the sexes and gives greater focus to the discrimination and unfair treatment that women experience. Mechanistic, reductionist, and simplistic ways of thinking will eventually produce a characteristic that is shared by all women and will simplify the reasons why women are controlled. Ecofeminism sheds light on the mechanisms that perpetuate male dominance, the hierarchical power dynamics within human society, and the disparities in power from a female perspective. This approach not only scrutinizes relationships between individuals, but also the connection between humans and the natural world. Through this lens, the link between mankind and nature can be explored, revealing the parallel between the subjugation of women and the exploitation of the environment. In order to truly embody the principles of ecofeminism, it must also embrace an 'ecological' mindset. This means recognizing the interconnectedness and interdependence of all elements within an ecosystem, promoting unity, integration, and equilibrium. Ecology encompasses the unique characteristics of individuals and their interactions within a system, while ecofeminism recognizes the interconnectedness of all living beings in the natural world and the significance of diversity. As a result, ecofeminism advocates for interconnected, multi-dimensional, and holistic

ways of thinking, rejecting mechanical, reductionist, and dualistic approaches. The relational perspective highlights the importance of the human-nature relationship to prevent conflict and division, the multidimensional perspective renews the focus on organisms and rejects notions of dominance and singularity, and the integration perspective challenges the abstract individual view and encourages a dialectical approach to understanding the relationship between individuals and the whole (Ling, 2014).

9. CONCLUSION

In the context of Pakistan, the research has explored the intricate confluence of gender perspectives, environmental concerns, and ecofeminism. The nation's environmental problems, which include pollution, biodiversity loss, and the effects of climate change, have all been carefully studied. This thorough comprehension of Pakistan's environmental problems has made it possible to investigate how ecofeminism may help to address these problems and advance sustainable practices. Two primary research topics were addressed by the systematic review: first, how ecofeminist principles ingrained in indigenous knowledge impact environmental management in Pakistan; and second, how ecofeminist themes promote environmental consciousness in Pakistani literature. The goals were thoughtfully crafted to investigate these issues using a thorough analysis of the literature, the work of non-governmental organizations, and the incorporation of ecofeminist ideas into laws and policies. The study determined and examined the important influence that ecofeminist ideals-aligned indigenous knowledge has on Pakistani environmental practices. A recurring topic was the intimate bond between women, their customs, and their innate affinity for the natural world. The study of two NGOs, namely LEAD and the Aurat Foundation, revealed their active efforts in promoting environmental consciousness, knowledge, and empowerment of women in Pakistan. The study recognized the need for gender-responsive governance and the potential influence of ecofeminist principles on sustainable development, highlighting opportunities and difficulties for ecofeminism in Pakistan. To sum up, this study offers insightful information about the complex interplay among

gender perspectives, environmental issues, and ecofeminism within Pakistan. The results highlight how crucial it is to include ecofeminist ideas and indigenous knowledge in environmental management literature, practices, and policy frameworks. To promote gender-responsive and ecofeminist governance in Pakistan, the study's recommendations give a path forward that can be followed in future research.

10. POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main approach used in this study was conducting desk research on international norms pertaining to gender equality, disaster risk reduction, and climate change. This involved analyzing international agreements, conventions, strategies, and other standards, as well as reports from academic institutions, general publications, and United Nations bodies. The study was primarily guided by the CEDAW Committee's GR37, which focuses on the relationship between gender, disaster risk reduction, and climate change and provides direction for States Parties in fulfilling their CEDAW obligations (Carrasco, 2021).

In GR37:

- Draws attention to the systemic injustices that affect women and girls, making it harder for them to adjust to the damaging effects of natural disasters and climate change.
- Presses States Parties to take decisive action to stop, lessen, and respond to natural disasters and climate change to guarantee that women's and girls' human rights are upheld, safeguarded, and realised.
- Stresses how crucial it is to approach national legislation using a "legislative framework" to implement the CEDAW and promote the resilience of women.
- Demands that States Parties address laws and policies that impact women's socioeconomic standing more broadly in addition to those that are specifically related to climate change and catastrophe risk, such as:
 - 1) Rights to substantive equality and non-discrimination,
 - 2) Rights to accountability and access to justice,
 - 3) Rights to work and social protection, and
 - 4) Rights to health and living standards.

- Emphasizes the importance of data collection and the monitoring and assessment of laws.

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